

A multilevel perspective on gender-based violence during the Covid-19 pandemic: the case of Italy

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Premise

This report has been produced within the framework of the project [Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems \(LEGITIMULT\)](#).² LEGITIMULT assesses the impact of the measures taken during the Covid-19 pandemic by international, national and subnational governments on multilevel institutions, intergovernmental relations, and on human rights and the principle of non-discrimination. To address this complex issue, ten partners in Europe and one in Canada share their expertise and research knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, public administration, as well as economy.

Problem-framing and salience of gender-based violence against women

In Italy, the scientific [focus on gender-based violence](#) has been greatly influenced by the concept of intersecting inequalities set out in the works published in the United States and through the social activism of the 1970s³. The earliest articles providing a theoretical approach to gender-based violence (GBV) were published in the 1980s and 1990s. Instead, the first years of the 21st century saw official recognition of the multidimensionality of violence, as well as the publication of national statistics reports from anti-violence centers⁴.

For what regards the international acknowledgement of the phenomenon, the Italian Government has signed several international agreements aimed at preventing and combating violence against women, including the [Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women \(CEDAW\)](#), ratified in 1985⁵.

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² LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01, GA Nr. 101061550.

³ Straus, M. A. (1976). Sexual inequality, cultural norms, and wife-beating. *Victimology*, 1, 54–70.

⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁵ CEDAW (1979) Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discriminations Against Women. New York: United Nations.

In addition, the 1993 [UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women](#), provided a comprehensive definition of GBV, as “any act [...] that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm to women[...]”⁶. Along these lines, GBV can also [manifest itself as](#) stalking, forced marriage, genital mutilation, sterilization, but also forced prostitution, selective malnourishment of female children, and dowry-related murder, both in the public and private spheres⁷.

The term [domestic violence](#) was adopted during the 1990s by women’s advocates to emphasize the private sphere of the phenomenon of interpersonal violence against women⁸. One of the most relevant definitions of domestic violence was outlined by the Council of Europe in the [Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence \(Istanbul Convention\)](#)⁹ and it entails any type of violence within the familiar nucleus (between parents, siblings, referencing guardians) or between present or past partners. The Convention refers to all dynamics that deny women of equality, safety, dignity, and fundamental freedoms; and specifically, it includes all acts that cause, might cause, or threaten to cause physical, sexual, psychological, or economic harm.

It is only in recent years that this phenomenon of domestic violence has been [adapted](#) to encompass any type of violence that occurs outside the marital bond, beyond heterosexuality, and refers also to occasional relationships¹⁰. From this idea of enlarging the scope of the concept of domestic violence outside the household dimension lies the term intimate partner violence (IPV). This label refers to the patterns of assaultive and coercive behaviors perpetrated by someone who is, was, or wishes to be intimately involved with the victim, whichever their gender is. Over the years, thanks to the growing interest in the topic among scholars of various disciplines, the list of elements considered within the definition of IPV has evolved. Differentiating among types of GBV represents the [starting point](#) for developing appropriate sanctions, treatment programs, legal and medical measures to face the peculiar

⁶ Resolution, General Assembly. *Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women*. New York: United Nations (1993). <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/declaration-elimination-violence-against-women>

⁷ UNICEF. (2000). *Violenza domestica sulle donne e bambine*. Innocenti Digest, 6, 1–28. Villardón-Gallego, L.; García-Cid, A.; Estévez, A.; García-Carrión, R. Early Educational Interventions to Prevent Gender-Based Violence: A Systematic Review. *Healthcare* 2023, 11, 142. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11010142>

⁸ Kelly, J. B., & Johnson, M. P. (2008). Differentiation Among Types of Intimate Partner Violence: Research Update and Implications for Interventions. *Family Court Review*, 46(3), 476–499. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-1617.2008.00215.x>

⁹ Council of Europe. *Convention on Preventing and Combatting Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence: Istanbul* (2011). <https://www.coe.int/en/web/gender-matters/council-of-europe-convention-on-preventing-and-combating-violence-against-women-and-domestic-violence>

¹⁰ Santoni, C. (2022). La violenza di genere agita e rappresentata nel mondo giovanile. *Fuori Luogo*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.6093/2723-9608/8683>

problems emerging from each case¹¹. Gender-based violence and IPV are a persistent societal issue, exacerbated during times of crisis, that primarily involves the victimization of women, both in terms of numbers and severity of consequences.

Regarding the scope of the phenomenon, the [latest data for the European Union](#) was published in 2024 by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) and the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE). Between 2020 and 2024, the study conducted 114,023 interviews with women living in all 27 Member States collecting information on their experiences of physical, sexual and psychological violence. According to the findings, one in five women in the EU (19.3%) have experienced physical violence, threats and/or sexual violence by a domestic perpetrator at some point in their lives. Among the participants, 17.7% have experienced physical or threats of physical or sexual violence by an intimate partner, and the number rises to 31.8% when psychological violence is included in the analysis. Notably, 14.6% of women indicate having experienced these acts more than once. Additionally, 5.1% of women have been victims of stalking from an intimate partner in their lifetime, while 13.6% of the participants have experienced it from perpetrators other than their partners. The study also reveals that 20.2% of women (24.8% in Italy) have experienced these physical and sexual harassments by people other than their partner since the age of 15; and 8.1% of the participants have experienced them two or more times from different perpetrators. Specifically, 12.9% of women in the EU have been victims of sexual violence (including rape) by a perpetrator other than their intimate since the age of 15. Sexual harassment is also significant: 30.8% of women in the EU have experienced it at least once in their lifetime, though the percentage is notably smaller in Italy (14.8%). Overall, the report shows that 30.7% of women have experienced psychological, physical, and/or sexual violence during their lifetime, with a percentage of 31.7 in Italy, with a high percentage of them being victims of the actions of their current or ex-partners¹².

Following the ratification of the *Istanbul Convention* (2013), Italy made a series of interventions aimed at establishing an integrated strategy to combat violence. The first intervention was made by Decree-Law No. 93 of 2013, which introduced significant changes in the criminal and procedural spheres and provided for the periodic adoption of national action plans against intimate partner violence against women. Moreover, the Italian legislation has progressed with measures such as the Law No. 119 (named *Law against Femicide*) of October 15, 2013, Law No. 69 (named *Red Code*) of July 19, 2019,

¹¹ Kelly, J. B., & Johnson, M. P. (2008). Differentiation Among Types of Intimate Partner Violence: Research Update and Implications for Interventions. Cit.

¹² FRA, Eurostat, EIGE- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), Eurostat and European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2024), EU Gender-based Violence Survey. <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2024/eu-gender-violence-survey-key-results>

and, more recently, Law No. 168 of November 24, 2023. These laws have introduced more effective measures against crimes indicative of gender-based violence and intimate partner violence. Moreover, all acts of sexual violence are prosecuted under Articles 609-bis and 612-bis of the Criminal Code, which punishes anyone who forces or induces a person to perform or undergo sexual acts through violence, threats, or abuse of authority.

In Italy, the enforcement of the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown measures heightened the vulnerability of women, many of whom were confined in the house with their abusers. The restrictive lockdown measures indeed led to a sharp increase in violence against women, as shown by extensive data from [ISTAT](#) – The National Statistics Institute, and other official sources, such as the official statistics institute of the autonomous province of Bolzano/Bozen ([ASTAT](#))¹³.

The analysis of this phenomenon reveals not only the dramatic human impact but also the critical role that political and legal factors have played in shaping responses across Italy's diverse regional landscape.

Against this backdrop, the main aim of this report is to give some evidence on how Italy's legal and institutional system responded to IPV against women during the Covid-19 pandemic. To achieve this, the report first offers an overview of the constitutional theory and reality of Italy's regional system. Such a parenthesis is necessary for the following reason: regions have a key role in implementing national policies to combat IPV against women. They can develop specific plans and programs, fund local services such as anti-violence centers, shelters, and psychological support services, as well as promote local awareness and training campaigns, collaborate with local authorities and associations, and monitor the effectiveness of initiatives. In short, the national government sets guidelines and funds the programs, while the regions implement them on the ground, adapting them to local needs, with the possibility to expand them. Both levels of government are key to combating GBV against women, to put national action plans into practice.

This report offers insights regarding the case study of the special-status region of Trentino- South Tyrol, focusing on its constituent parts: the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen (Alto Adige/Südtirol, South Tyrol) and the Autonomous Province of Trento (Trentino).

¹³ Italian National Institute of Statistics. *Violence against women*. <https://www.istat.it/en/statistical-themes/focus/violence-against-women/>; *Violenza sulle donne—Centri di ascolto anti violenza e case donna—2020 | Pubblicazioni e statistiche varie su diversi temi*. (n.d.). <https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/pubblicazioni/violenza-sulle-donne-centri-di-ascolto-anti-violenza-e-case-donna-2020>;

Constitutional and Political Framework

Italy is a regional state that blends [unitary and federal features](#), with a persistent [North-South divide](#) that comes with varying degrees of [fiscal capacities](#)¹⁴ from one to another subnational entity (i.e. regions, provinces, metropolitan cities, and municipalities); the regions are the main subnational players in the political system of asymmetric regionalism. Five regions have a special status (established in 1948 or shortly after) and fifteen ordinary ones (established only in the 1970s with further reform seasons in the late 1990s). Of the five special regions, three – Aosta Valley, Trentino-South Tyrol and Friuli Venezia Giulia – owe their [special status](#) to the presence of historical and territorially concentrated linguistic¹⁵.

Compared to ordinary regions, the special regions enjoy [quasi-federal relations](#) with the national government, although not all have managed to set up genuine self-government¹⁶. Their basic laws (statutes) have constitutional status and special amendment procedures. Ordinary regions adopt their statutes with a special regional law. For the most part, these statutes regulate the form of government and the basic principles of the region's organization and functioning. The powers of ordinary regions are enshrined in the Italian Constitution (Const.). Article 117(2) lists powers falling within the exclusive competence of the state (the national level of government); article 117(3) enumerates powers shared by the state and the regions (including education, health protection and co-ordination of public finance); and article 117(4) assigns residual powers to the regions. In the shared areas, the Const. vests legislative powers in the regions, with the national parliament laying down the fundamental principles governing these powers.

In constitutional reality, regional autonomy is (heavily) conditioned by, first and foremost, the financial relations that each region has with the center and by the underutilized and dysfunctional system of intergovernmental relations, i.e. the consultative, multilateral system of executive conferences compensating for the fact that Italy's second chamber, the Senate, does not represent subnational

¹⁴ For details see: Alber, E./Valdesalici, A. (2023). Italy, in: Jean-François Tremblay (ed.), *The Forum of Federations Handbook of Fiscal Federalism*, Palgrave Macmillan, Cham, 257-294. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-97258-5_7 and for a focus on local government: Valdesalici, A./Trettel, M. (2023). The System of Local Government in Italy: A Stress-Test to Traditional Paradigms?, in: Matteo Nicolini and Alice Valdesalici (eds.), *Local Governance in Multi-Layered Systems*, Ius Gentium: Comparative Perspectives on Law and Justice, vol 108. Springer, Cham, 261-282. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-41792-4_12

¹⁵ Alber, E. (2022). Language Realities and Policies in Italy: Multifaceted, Multilevel, Asymmetric. *Forum of Federations* <https://hdl.handle.net/10863/25576>

¹⁶ Palermo, F./Valdesalici, A. (2019). Irreversibly Different. A Country Study of Constitutional Asymmetry in Italy. In: Popelier, P., Sahadžić, M. (eds.) *Constitutional Asymmetry in Multinational Federalism*. Federalism and Internal Conflicts. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11701-6_11

entities. In essence, Italy's institutional framework excludes regions from the national legislative process and its multi-party centralized political system, dominated by coalitions, has led to [partisan control of regional institutions](#).

National Measures

In April 2020, then-Minister for Family and Equal Opportunities, Elena Bonetti, decided to release 30 million euros to combat male violence against women. However, the funds provided by the Department for Equal Opportunities have had difficulties reaching the regions that do not apply any action plan to combat GBV. While the dialogue between civil society and the government on an institutional level does exist, it still has a few problems and shortages. The problem is the [difficulty of dialogue](#) between the state and the regions to have an effective and prompt response¹⁷.

A [National Anti-Violence Network](#)¹⁸ exists in Italy to support women victims of violence. It is a project to support women victims of violence that offers, since 2009, a 'call center' service through the telephone number: 1522. This helpline remained an essential channel during the lockdown for women seeking help, especially with the launch of online chat during the lockdown. According to the [Department for Equal Opportunities](#), the number of total requests from March to May increased almost three times in 2020 compared to 2019. And, broadly, the number of people who contacted 1522 doubled in the same three months.

There was a substantial increase in IPV in Italy during the pandemic, particularly in the early months of lockdown. The national network [D.i.Re – Donne in Rete contro la Violenza](#) (Women on the Net Against Violence) [reported](#) 2,867 women contacted 80 shelters between March 2 and April 5, 2020 – a 74.5% increase compared to 2018 monthly averages¹⁹. Despite this increase, the number of first-time contacts dropped significantly, suggesting many [women were unable to reach help](#) for the first time due to heightened control by perpetrators²⁰.

¹⁷ Donato, S. (2020). *Gender-Based Violence against Women in Intimate and Couple Relationships. The Case of Spain and Italy during the COVID-19 Pandemic Lockdown*. Italian Sociological Review, 10(3S), 869. <https://italiansociologicalreview.com/ojs/index.php/ISR/article/view/402>

¹⁸ Rete Nazionale Antiviolenza a sostegno delle donne vittime di violenza | Ministero dell'Interno. (n.d.). <http://www.interno.gov.it/it/contatti/rete-nazionale-antiviolenza-sostegno-donne-vittime-violenza>

¹⁹ D.i.Re, Donne in Rete contro la violenza. (2020). Report Annuale Rilevazione dati 2020. Tratto da https://www.direcontrolaviolenza.it/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Report_Dati-DiRe_2020-1.pdf Bellizzi, S., Nivoli, A., Loretto, L., Farina, G., Ramses, M., & Ronzoni, A. R. (2020). Violence against women in Italy during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International journal of gynecology and obstetrics: the official organ of the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 150(2), 258–259. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.13270>

²⁰ D.i.Re, Donne in Rete contro la violenza. (2020). Report Annuale Rilevazione dati 2020. Cit.

Increased contact with anti-violence centers later was attributed to public awareness campaigns such as [#nonseisola](#) (“you are not alone”) and [#escidalsilenzio](#) (“come out from the silence”) broadcast nationwide in April 2020. This increase is also linked to heightened visibility of help services, which were actively promoted through Italian national television and across the Internet. It is interesting to note that the type of violence that people are asking for help with via chat or call is mostly physical violence perpetrated by their partner, followed by psychological violence. A [multicenter survey](#) from five Italian anti-violence centers found that nearly 28% of women cohabiting with abusers experienced an increase in IPV during lockdown, while the victimization decreased for those who did not live with a partner (56% of the sample); however, over 60% of the entire sample reported facing threats or coercion, and many reporting sexual abuse²¹.

The [case of Lorena Quaranta](#)²², a young medical student murdered by her partner in March 2020, provoked a strong public reaction. Though initially sentenced to life imprisonment, the [Court of Cassation](#) – the Supreme Court at the top of the ordinary jurisdiction later – cited Covid-19 stress as a mitigating factor²³; a controversial decision that triggered [national outrage](#) and concern among women’s rights groups²⁴.

Despite the legislative efforts introduced as a response to IPV during the pandemic, several governance challenges remained. The degree of responsiveness in Italy has been less dynamic compared to that of other European countries, such as Spain. Poor coordination between the national government and regions led to [delays in the implementation of urgent measures](#) and in the disbursement of allocated funds²⁵.

In the research and institutional area, Italy has also made efforts and achieved a certain level of success to inquire into GBV. In both the 17th and 18th legislatures, the Senate established [Commissions of Inquiry](#) on femicide and gender-based violence, which have conducted extensive investigations into the phenomenon²⁶. A [report published on 6 September 2022](#), addressed issues including education,

²¹ Romito, P., Pellegrini, M., & Saurel-Cubizolles, M.J. (2022). Intimate Partner Violence Against Women During the COVID-19 Lockdown in Italy: A Multicenter Survey Involving Anti-Violence Centers. *Violence Against Women*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9051993/>

²² *Scrutinizing the Italian Court of Cassation’s Decision to Recognize Pandemic-Related Stress as a Mitigating Factor in Femicide*. (2024, August 22). <https://www.jurist.org/commentary/2024/08/scrutinizing-the-italian-court-of-cassations-decision-to-recognize-pandemic-related-stress-as-a-mitigating-factor-in-femicide/>

²³ Corte Cass., I sez. penale, sent., 9 Luglio 2024, n. 27115. Estratta come allegato da Il Diritto – quotidiano Dike <https://ildiritto.it/penale/omicidio-lorena-quaranta-sentenza-annullata-per-stress-da-covid/>.

²⁴ *Scrutinizing the Italian Court of Cassation’s Decision to Recognize Pandemic-Related Stress as a Mitigating Factor in Femicide*. (2024, August 22), cit.

²⁵ Donato, S. (2020). *Gender-Based Violence against Women in Intimate and Couple Relationships*. Cit.

²⁶ IMPRODOVA Project. (2022) *National Frameworks in Italy*. <https://training.improdova.eu/en/national-frameworks-in-italy/>

women's health, treatment programs for perpetrators, and the functioning of anti-violence centers during the Covid-19 pandemic. In parallel, the Ministry of Health launched the project [#lpaziaCCM2021](#), which focuses on training health and social-health professionals in the prevention of violence, with particular attention to the challenges that emerged during the pandemic²⁷.

In addition, most importantly, in 2022 the [supply of Anti-Violence Centers](#) (CAVs) increased: in total there are 385 +3.2% compared to 2021, +37% compared to 2017 (first year of the Survey). CAVs (in 83.7% of cases) have activated new forms of communication targeting women: in particular, communication via email, written messages, and use of social media have been introduced since the pandemic period. Moreover, 85.1% of CAVs adhere to territorial networks: the stronger the territorial network of governance, the greater the capacity of CAVs to offer services to women. In 2022, there were 60,751 women who contacted anti-violence centers at least once, an increase of 7.8 percent compared to 2021 and 39.8 percent compared to 2017, a figure similar to the increase in CAVs in the territory²⁸.

The Rise of Interpersonal Violence Against Women during Covid-19

While in the first half of 2020 the Central Directorate of Criminal Police recorded a general decrease in crimes against persons, with a sharp drop in homicides, the [number of femicides remained almost stable](#): in 2019 there were 56 women killed between January and July, while in 2020 there were 59 (the increase particularly concerns the month of January)²⁹.

Before the Covid-19 pandemic, calls to Italy's national 1522 hotline were already concerning but relatively stable. However, followed by a few weeks of silence, the lockdown period (March–May 2020) registered a [dramatic and unprecedented surge](#): calls rose by 73% compared to the same months in 2019³⁰. Specifically, March 2020 saw 2,038 calls compared to 1,104 in March 2019; April 2020 experienced an even [sharper spike](#) with 5,031 calls versus 1,245 in April 2019; and May 2020 recorded 3,718 calls compared to 1,276 the previous year³¹. These numbers combined reveal how between March and October 2020, a total of 15,128 women contacted the 1522 service. Alarming, 45.3% of these women reported experiencing violence for the first time, suggesting that the pandemic did not

²⁷ Progetto *lpazia Ccm 2021* | CCM - Network. <https://www.ccm-network.it/pagina.jsp?id=node/2399>

²⁸ Dipartimento per le Pari Opportunità, 2023, I CENTRI ANTIVIOLENZA E LE DONNE CHE HANNO AVVIATO IL PERCORSO DI USCITA DALLA VIOLENZA Anno 2022. <https://www.istat.it/it/files/2023/11/reportCAV.pdf>

²⁹ Istat (2021), *Omicidi di donne*, <https://www.istat.it/statistiche-per-temi/focus/violenza-sulle-donne/il-fenomeno/omicidi-di-donne/>

³⁰ Donato, S. (2020). *Gender-Based Violence against Women in Intimate and Couple Relationships*. Cit.

³¹ *Violenza di genere al tempo del Covid-19: Le chiamate al numero di pubblica utilità 1522 (2020)* Istat. <https://www.istat.it/comunicato-stampa/violenza-di-genere-al-tempo-del-covid-19-le-chiamate-al-numero-verde-1522/>

merely intensify existing abusive dynamics but also created [new cases of IPV](#)³². Of the total calls, 60% were made by the victims, while 36.1% were made by concerned acquaintances or family members.

Looking at reports to the prosecutor's offices, the "[Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry into Femicide, as well as all forms of Gender-based Violence](#)"³³ accounts a decrease in reports of crimes of gender-based violence in March and April, i.e., the months of greatest social containment, and a significant increase in the period thereafter. Finally, regarding the [reception of women by Anti-Violence Centers](#) (CAVs), there does not appear to be a significant increase, although 8.6% of the requests reportedly concerned incidents that women trace precisely to the pandemic³⁴.

Data collected from court offices between August 1, 2019, and July 31, 2020, also show that the percentage of cases registered for the crime of mistreatment against family members and cohabitants increased by 11%. The decrease in reports of mistreatment is mainly related to the increased control implemented by partners and cohabiting family members resulting from confinement in the home³⁵. Moreover, when considering additional familial relationships, including fathers or other relatives, the total rises to 93% of cases occurring within the family setting. Only 7% of perpetrators were acquaintances, emphasizing the intimate context of these violent acts. Most of the violence is perpetrated by intimate partners or ex-partners. Specifically, 63% of cases involve current partners (husbands, cohabitants, or boyfriends), while 21% involve ex-partners. This highlights the domestic nature of such violence.

The [characteristics of women seeking assistance from anti-violence centers](#) have remained consistent over the years. More than half (55%) of these women are aged between 30 and 49 years. There has been a slight increase in the percentage of minors seeking help, rising from 4% in 2020 to 5% in 2021. Conversely, the percentage of women aged 20-29 decreased from 24% to 23% during the same period. The proportions of women over 50 and 60 years old have remained stable at 13% and 5%, respectively³⁶.

³² *Ibidem*.

³³ Commissione parlamentare di inchiesta sul femminicidio, nonché su ogni forma di violenza di genere (2020), Doc XXII bis n. 2 - Relazione sui dati riguardanti la violenza di genere e domestica nel periodo di applicazione delle misure di contenimento per l'emergenza da COVID-19, disponibile al link <http://www.senato.it/Leg18/20301> (14/05/2020)

³⁴ Istat (2021), *Le richieste di aiuto durante la pandemia*, <https://www.istat.it/comunicato-stampa/le-richieste-di-aiuto-durante-la-pandemia-i-dati-dei-centri-antiviolenza-delle-case-rifugio-e-delle-chiamate-al-1522/>

³⁵ Dipartimento per le Pari Opportunità, (2021) L'effetto della pandemia sulla violenza di genere. Anno 2020-2021.

³⁶ *Violenza sulle donne: Centri antiviolenza e strutture residenziali - 2023 | Pubblicazioni e statistiche varie. Su diversi temi.* (n.d.). Istituto provinciale di statistica ASTAT, <https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/pubblicazioni/violenza-sulle-donne-centri-antiviolenza-e-strutture-residenziali-2023>

Economic Restraints and Institutional Responses

The lockdown and quarantine measures during the Covid-19 pandemic have exacerbated situations of domestic violence. [Reports](#) indicate that 8.6% of violence cases were linked to pandemic-related stressors, such as forced cohabitation and job loss³⁷. [The pandemic's economic impact hit women disproportionately](#). Women comprised 58% of the temporary workforce and 66% of part-time workers, often concentrated in sectors most affected by the lockdown.

Daniela Del Boca's analysis underscores the pandemic's adverse impact on female employment, labeling it a "[she-cession](#)"³⁸. Women were disproportionately affected by job losses, particularly in sectors heavily impacted by mobility restrictions, such as hospitality and retail. Although governmental interventions like the "[Cura Italia](#)" (*Cure Italy*) package were introduced, women faced greater difficulty re-entering the workforce. Compounding these challenges, school closures placed additional burdens on women, limiting their mobility and increasing domestic responsibilities, as they often assumed primary childcare duties³⁹.

In January 2021, the independent NGO *WeWorld*, in collaboration with *Ipsos Group S.A.*, administered a survey to a representative sample of Italian women aged from 18 to 65 to explore the [impact of the Covid-19 crisis on female economic condition](#). The analysis revealed that 50% of women experienced a decrease in income. Specifically, among women aged 25 to 34.63% reported a decrease, while 60% of those aged 45 to 54 noted a reduction in their income. Additionally, 24% of the younger group and 21% of the older group experienced losses greater than 50%. Moreover, the study highlighted that 60% of both employed and non-employed women with children saw their economic income reduced by more than 50% due to the pandemic. Over 40% of women reported increased economic dependence on family or partners, and nearly 50% stated that their family's economic resources were scarce or insufficient in the last 12 months. Almost 40% of women indicated difficulties in covering unexpected expenses, with 14% struggling to afford school materials for their children. Concerns about job security were also prevalent, with almost 1 in 2 women fearing job loss, rising to 55% among young women and 54% among employed women with young children aged 0-13. In conclusion, the results of the research conducted by *WeWorld* proved that the health restrictions introduced during the Covid-19 pandemic

³⁷ LINEE DI INDIRIZZO 2023-24 / File comunicati stampa / Media—Ufficio Stampa della Provincia autonoma di Trento. (n.d.). <https://www.ufficiostampa.provincia.tn.it/Media/File-comunicati-stampa/LINEE-DIINDIRIZZO-2023-24> Dossier con Dati e Testimonianze. Donne e Covid-19. La pandemia delle disuguaglianze (2022, Marzo. Caritas Italiana. <https://www.caritas.it/dossier-con-dati-e-testimonianze/>

³⁸ Del Boca, D. 2022. *L'impatto del Covid-19 sul divario di genere in Italia* Fondazione per la cittadinanza attiva. <https://fondaca.org/index.php/it/table6/60-l-impatto-del-covid-19-sul-divario-di-genere-in-italia>

³⁹ Caselli, F./F. Grigoli/D. Sandri/A. Spilimbergo (2021): Mobility under the COVID-19 pandemic: asymmetric effects across gender and age, in: IMF Economic Review, 1–34.

had a negative influence on the economic situation of women, already critical beforehand; they had to take on an increased role in care and family work, which was followed by a higher exposure to IPV risks⁴⁰.

[Family dynamics were also strained](#). The closure of schools placed additional caregiving responsibilities on women, who already shouldered 74% of domestic work and care duties in Italy⁴¹. Victims had reduced chances to access traditional support spaces, such as workplaces, schools, or community centers, thereby intensifying the risks associated with IPV victimization. Therefore, in addition to the resurgence of pre-existing violence, the socio-economic consequences of the crisis triggered by the health emergency, such as [forced cohabitation or loss of employment](#) for the perpetrator or the victim, may have increased the risk of violent behavior⁴². For example, according to a recent [report by D.i.Re – Donne in Rete contro la Violenza](#), one in three women who turn to the more than 80 anti-violence centers in their network is on zero income (32.9%), and less than 40 percent can count on a secure income⁴³.

On December 3, 2020 following protocol was signed: [Protocollo di Intesa](#) (Memorandum of Understanding) on “*Microcredito di libertà – Protocollo di Microcredito per l’emancipazione economica delle donne che hanno subito violenza*” (Freedom Micro-credit - Micro-credit protocol for the economic empowerment of women who have been subject to violence). It has been targeting women in particular conditions of vulnerability and social and financial exclusion who are unable to meet personal and family needs. [Caritas](#), as part of the Project, has committed to support and implement the activities of diocesan Caritas already engaged in assisting women victims of violence, strengthening their skills through staff training, and socio-legal assistance⁴⁴.

Case Study of the Special Region of Trentino-South Tyrol

The Italian Constitution in art. 116 provides special forms and conditions of autonomy for the regions of Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Sicily, Trentino-South Tyrol and Aosta Valley, but, unlike in the other

⁴⁰ *WeWorld*, La condizione economica femminile in epoca di Covid-19, marzo 2021, cfr. <https://www.weworld.it/news-e-storie/news/la-condizione-economica-femminile-in-epoca-di-covid-19>

⁴¹ ISTAT (2021) Data on violence against women. <https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/257704>

⁴² Dossier con Dati e Testimonianze. Donne e Covid-19. La pandemia delle diseguglianze (2022, Marzo. *Caritas Italiana*. <https://www.caritas.it/dossier-con-dati-e-testimonianze/>

⁴³ Dossier con Dati e Testimonianze. Donne e Covid-19. La pandemia delle diseguglianze (2022, Marzo. *Caritas Italiana*. <https://www.caritas.it/dossier-con-dati-e-testimonianze/>; https://www.direcontrolaviolenza.it/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Report_Dati-DiRe_2020-1.pdf

⁴⁴ *Il sostegno economico alle vittime della violenza di genere*. (n.d.). Dipartimento per le Pari Opportunità. <http://www.pariopportunita.gov.it/it/politiche-e-attivita/violenza-di-genere/il-sostegno-economico-alle-vittime-della-violenza-di-genere/>

four special regions, in Trentino-South Tyrol, most competences are vested with the two autonomous provinces Bolzano/Bozen and Trento and not with the special region. The entry into force of the Second Autonomy Statute on 20 January 1972⁴⁵ had three effects that would characterize the politics of Trentino and South Tyrol in the years to come.

First, the region of Trentino-South Tyrol from then on retained only a few competences that over the years have been further devolved to, and differently exercised by, the two autonomous provinces. Second, Trentino and South Tyrol, even if formally under the same 'regional roof' (i.e., governed by the same autonomy statute), developed different political systems. In South Tyrol, a consociational democracy system model based on ethnic separation and proportional representation is in place, while Trentino is characterized by a majoritarian system with the direct election of the president. Third, having competences at provincial level ultimately enabled South Tyrol to implement the provisions establishing the ethnic quota system (i.e., equitable distribution of civil service posts and resources between the major language groups) and guaranteeing the use of the German language in the public sphere (i.e., bilingualism in the administration and judiciary and the right to mother tongue education).

The case of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen

The provincial government of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen has adopted strategic documents to track progress in eliminating violence against women and girls. [Law n. 13/2021](#) seeks to create a violence-free environment, condemning all forms of violence and supporting training and awareness initiatives. It emphasizes the need for collaboration among various entities to achieve its objectives, promoting awareness campaigns and regulating public-private partnerships. The [Casa delle Donne](#) (*House of Women*) service plays a crucial role in providing support services, including shelters and counseling for women facing violence. A permanent coordination table has been established to integrate policies for violence victims, meeting at least twice a year to discuss law implementation and coordination. The three-year plan prioritizes expanding *Casa delle Donne* services and includes a thematic table for migrant women victims of violence. The territorial anti-violence network promotes cooperation among public and private entities, with municipalities appointing contact persons for violence-related issues. The provincial statistics institute (ASTAT) is responsible for collecting and analyzing data on violence, enhancing understanding of the situation. The province can join as a civil party in femicide and violence cases, aiming to provide integrated information on violence against women.

⁴⁵ It was adopted by constitutional law no. 1 of 10 November 1971.

In short, Law n. 13/2021 offers a comprehensive framework for preventing GBV, advocating for a coordinated approach involving multiple stakeholders, and suggesting the need for increased resources and transparency in civil party participation, while also considering measures for vulnerable groups, including non-binary individuals⁴⁶.

The Covid-19 pandemic has significantly influenced the landscape of IPV in South Tyrol, as evidenced by a notable [increase in the number of women seeking assistance](#) from anti-violence centers, with 586 women receiving support in 2021. This surge indicates that the pandemic exacerbated existing vulnerabilities, prompting more women to reach out for help during a time of crisis⁴⁷. The total number of services provided by these centers rose to 5,451 in 2021; and compared to the year 2020, there is a sharp increase in legal consultations (+88%) and in telephone consultations (+31%). This statistic underscores the urgent need for resources dedicated to addressing gender-based violence during the pandemic⁴⁸. The nature of violence reported remained predominantly domestic, with 93% of cases occurring within the family, highlighting how the pandemic intensified domestic violence situations, as victims were confined with their abusers, leading to a rise in incidents of violence⁴⁹. Additionally, there was a [demographic shift](#) in the women seeking help, with an increase in younger women (20-29 years) and older women (60 years and above) reaching out for support. This change suggests that the pandemic affected various age groups differently, emphasizing the need for tailored interventions to address the unique challenges faced by these demographics⁵⁰. The reintegration of women after shelter stays was complicated by the pandemic, as 29% returned to their previous homes with the perpetrator. In fact, the challenges faced by women in escaping violent situations during a time when resources and support systems were strained, further complicating their circumstances⁵¹. Overall, the data from ASTAT over the years reveals that the pandemic has had a profound impact on IPV violence in South Tyrol, necessitating a reevaluation of support systems and intervention strategies to effectively address this pressing issue.

⁴⁶<https://assets-eu-01.kc-usercontent.com/c9a59f24-f147-0146-30a4-7f9876ae560c/1079b38b-fd28-4162-9c02-7047506ee07f/2024.07.25%20Bericht%20Umsetz.%20LG13-21%20it.pdf>

⁴⁷ ASTAT. *Violenza sulle donne: Centri antiviolenza e strutture residenziali - 2023 | Pubblicazioni e statistiche varie su diversi temi.* <https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/pubblicazioni/violenza-sulle-donne-centri-antiviolenza-e-strutture-residenziali-2023>

⁴⁸ *Ibidem.*

⁴⁹ ASTAT. *Violenza sulle donne: Centri antiviolenza e strutture residenziali - 2022 | Pubblicazioni e statistiche varie su diversi temi.* <https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/pubblicazioni/violenza-sulle-donne-centri-antiviolenza-e-strutture-residenziali-2022>

⁵⁰ ASTAT. *Violenza sulle donne: Centri antiviolenza e strutture residenziali - 2023 | Pubblicazioni e statistiche varie su diversi temi.* Cit.

⁵¹ *Ibidem.*

The case of the Autonomous Province of Trento

For what regards the case of the Autonomous Province of Trento, similarly to other regions, the lockdown has increased the isolation of women and therefore their difficulties in taking advantage of support networks. Official data published from the [Unit of Violence and Crime Prevention](#) (UMSe) of the Autonomous Province of Trento reveal a decline in the data collected by the authorities and support centers. According to the information gathered by the anti-violence services in the area during 2021, there had been a rise in requests for both housing (+14.4% of entrances) and non-housing support services compared to the prior year. For example, compared to the 614 complaints and warnings reported in 2021, in 2020, they registered 475 cases; complaints decreased by 22.5%. At the same time, in 2021 the count of admonition proceedings increased by 60.7% compared to 2020, but showed a general decrease compared to the average of the years 2015-2019. Another relevant aspect that can be interpreted as a consequence of the restrictions and the elevated risks of living with the abusive partner, is the number of women who accessed the emergency room due to injuries inflicted by their partner. In 2020, the women who needed medical assistance because of IPV were 428, a smaller number than the data collected during 2019 (528) and 2021 (365). The differences reflect the limited, but present, impossibility of women to access the medical system to seek help. In conclusion, these numbers reveal how, despite the services still available to the victims of IPV, the pandemic reduced their chances to report their experiences and ask for help⁵².

For what regards the number contacts made to the national helpline 1522, the data collected in Trentino across 2020 and 2021 revealed a peak in demand, trend confirmed at the national level. From the 16 thousand women making use of the service, 113 of them came from the Province of Trento. The report recently published by the Equal Opportunities Commission and curated by Anna Ressa e Letizia Caporusso (2025) displays clearly the differences in the trend of calls across the national and provincial level, revealing an overall consistency between the two⁵³.

The [CambiaMenti](#) pathway was a group initiative promoted by the local anti-violence services operational network that provided a safe space for perpetrators of violence against women who voluntarily participated in group debates with professionals. The program saw 18 men participate in

⁵²https://www.ufficiostampa.provincia.tn.it/content/download/232156/3708659/file/LINEE_DI_INDIRIZZO_2023-24_per_stampa.pdf; Provincia autonoma di Trento, Agenzia per la Coesione sociale, Umse pari opportunità, prevenzione della violenza e della criminalità, 2022

⁵³ Ressa A./Caporusso, L. (2025) *(Dis)parità tra donne e uomini in trentino indicatori e analisi*. Relazione della Commissione provinciale Pari Opportunità tra donna e uomo sullo stato di attuazione della legge provinciale sulle Pari Opportunità e sull'andamento delle politiche di genere in Trentino. Commissione Pari Opportunità, Consiglio della Provincia Autonoma di Trento.

the preliminary interviews provided to access the service in 2020 (compared to 24 men in 2019), and among them, 11 took the pathway (16 men in 2019). The decrease in participation in the service does not necessarily reflect a regression in IPV perpetration, it rather mirrors a momentary decline in the requests, possibly due to the lack of access to the service because of the restrictions implemented during the lockdown phases. The service was, however, shut down in 2020 due to the discontinuation of public funding. On the other hand, since 2015, the province has been offering training courses and programs to help men avoid and reduce violent behavior at its Centers for Men Who Commit Violence (CUAV). During the Covid-19 pandemic, however, these centers have helped significantly fewer men. This reduction, followed by a subsequent increase in the following years, appears to be a possible consequence of the restrictions imposed to reduce infections during lockdown⁵⁴.

Finally, in March 2020 the prosecutor's office in Trento recalled and requested the application of [alternative housing solutions](#) for IPV victims following the urging of the Domestic Affair Minister and article 384 bis of the Code of Criminal Procedure. The Prosecutor's statement demanded the removal of the abuser from the home, not the victims and their children. This solution was intended to reduce the exposure of women and victimized individuals, not only to Covid infection, but also to the trauma of moving to a shelter⁵⁵.

Concluding remarks

The Covid-19 pandemic acted as a magnifying glass, exposing and exacerbating institutional weaknesses and gender inequalities in Italy's response to intimate partner violence (IPV). Women who are confined with their abusers are extremely vulnerable, as seen by the sharp rise in hotline calls and the drop in official reports during lockdown. The statistics also demonstrate the resilience of anti-violence networks and the success of public awareness campaigns in facilitating access to support services. However, the Italian reaction was delayed by poor institutional coordination, delayed money distribution, and inconsistent regional implementation, despite the fact that national initiatives (such as emergency funding, the strengthening of helpline services, and public campaigns) played a significant role in preventing IPV. The overall efficacy of the reaction was restrained by these coordination problems, especially between the national and regional levels.

The case of Trentino-South Tyrol demonstrates how important regional and provincial administrations are in supporting the successful execution of national policies within Italy's multilevel governance framework. The pandemic led to delayed or disjointed answers to victims' requests, even in areas with

⁵⁴ Ressa A. & Caporusso, L. (2025) *(Dis)parita' tra donne e uomini in trentino indicatori e analisi*. cit.

⁵⁵ <https://www.trentotoday.it/attualita/violenza-donne-dati-trentino-2021.html>

ample resources, exposing enduring flaws in intergovernmental coordination. However, as seen by the expansion and digitization of Anti-Violence Centers (CAVs), services were more efficient and available in regions with robust territorial networks. Many of the holes were filled by civil society organizations, and national awareness campaigns were successful in reestablishing support systems for women.

The economic repercussions of the epidemic also made it more difficult for women to escape violent circumstances and exacerbated their dependency. In addition to making them more vulnerable, the increase in economic instability highlighted the connection between economic precarity and gender-based violence, particularly for younger women and working moms.

In the end, this report urges a renewed dedication to gender-sensitive crisis response techniques. The integration of economic support measures into anti-violence initiatives, timely and equitable resource distribution, enhanced institutional coordination between state and regional authorities, and the fortification of territorial networks that offer survivors direct assistance are a few examples. The report's conclusions demonstrate the necessity of consistent funding for governance improvements in order to guarantee that safeguards are available during emergencies like lockdowns.